

Postoperative Airway Emergency following Accidental Flexometallic Tube Transection

Karim Habib MR¹, Bhattacharyya Prithwis², Yunus Md³

1. MD, DNB, IDCCM, Senior Resident, 2. MD, PDCC, Professor & Head, 3. MD Additional Professor

Department of Anaesthesiology, Critical Care and Pain Medicine
North Eastern Indira Gandhi Regional Institute of Health and Medical Science
Shillong, Meghalaya, India

Correspondence: Habib Md Reazaul Karim (drhabibkarim@gmail.com)

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About the Author: Habib Md Reazaul Karim did graduation from Assam Medical College, Dibrugarh and MD (Anaesthesiology) from North Eastern Indira Gandhi Regional Institute of Health and Medical Sciences, Shillong. He has also done DNB in Anaesthesiology and Indian Diploma in Critical Care Medicine (IDCCM). Currently he is working as a senior resident at NEIGRIHMS, Shillong. His areas of interests are pharmacoeconomics, cardiothoracic anaesthesia, critical care medicine and researches in perioperative medicine.

Abstract: Endotracheal intubation using flexometallic tubes are often required in anaesthesia practice for a variety of reasons. It is preferred in the head and neck region surgeries due to its relative resistance to kinking forces. At times, these patients postoperatively may need to be shifted to ICU or HDU without extubation for further stabilization/management and extubation after adequate recovery. We present an unusual accident where a new flexometallic endotracheal tube was permanently tapered, transected and migrated proximally due to patient's bite on tube leading to airway emergency in post-operative recovery period.

Key-Words: flexometallic tube transection, airway obstruction

Introduction: Endotracheal intubation is commonly done during General Anaesthesia (GA) in surgical patients. Many times patients are shifted to Intensive Care Unit (ICU) or High Dependence Unit (HDU) without extubation for further management and extubation is done after sufficient recovery from surgery and anaesthesia. Post-thyroidectomy tracheomalacia is one of the complications after surgery in patients with large goiter pressing on the trachea.¹ Such patients are usually extubated after sufficient recovery from anaesthesia and bed side testing for leak in HDU. During the recovery phase, endotracheal tube bite by patients is common. Flexometallic tubes are reinforced with stainless steel wire and expected to be relatively resistant to kinking external forces. Transaction of

the tube is rare and significant damage to flexometallic tube is hardly reported in the literature. We present such a case with due consent from the patient.

Case Report: A 26 year old girl of American Society of Anaesthesiologists physical class-II, presented with a large multinodular colloid goiter for subtotal thyroidectomy. Airway examination revealed Mallampati score II with inter-incisor distance of 4 cm and normal jaw, neck movements and dentition. Thyromental and sternomental distance were 6.5 cm and 14 cm respectively. Surgery was performed under GA using a new, single use 7.5mmID cuffed flexometallic endotracheal tube. The surgery and anaesthesia were uneventful. Though preoperative airway examination was not suggestive of anticipated difficult airway, clinical examination and X-ray revealed tracheal compression. It was therefore decided to shift the patient postoperatively to HDU and extubate the patient after full recovery from anaesthesia after performing bedside “leak tests” for assessing tracheomalacia and for further management. In the post-operative period, the patient was recovering well but was biting the tube (there was no bite block in situ). Before the leak tests could be performed, attending staff nurse informed that the half of the tube had come out of mouth and patient was having obstructed type of breathing. Immediate examination revealed that the flexometallic tube was transected and the distal part had migrated proximally about 2.5 cm from the incisor (Figure 1). Luckily, the distal part was still connected with reinforced wire (Figure 2) which prevented further migration and its consequences as an endotracheal foreign body. As patient was fully awake and co-operative, the flexometallic tube was taken out keeping the intubation trolley and airway exchange catheter standby. Patient did not show any feature of post extubation tracheomalacia and airway obstruction and was discharged to the ward next day.

Figure 1: Showing the transected flexometallic tube. The proximal segment has migrated towards oropharynx.

Figure 2: The two segments are connected with reinforced wire with kinked and tapered air entry end

Discussion: Flexometallic tubes are flexible and relatively resistant to kinking and external force. Therefore, they have an advantage over other tubes in head and neck surgeries. However, one criticism of orally placed flexometallic tube is that they should never be left postoperatively because once crushed they can cause total airway obstruction by remaining kinked.² Though this can be

taken as an “expert recommendation”, it is not feasible for low income countries like India where per capita public expenditure on health is only 712 Indian rupees.³ Changing flexometallic tube with another PVC tube for just a few hours till recovery would have cost another hundred rupees. So, often flexometallic tubes are continued in to the post-operative period till the patient recovers completely.

Endotracheal tube malfunction during the perioperative period is an emergency for the anaesthesiologist. Accidental transection of flexometallic tube is rarely reported in the literature. One case of accidental transection of an armoured nasal endotracheal tube (ETT) with an osteotome during surgery for Crouzon syndrome was described by Murthy et al.⁴ and another case of accidental transection of flexometallic ETT with Gigli-saw during partial maxillectomy was described by Ladi et al.⁵ Both the cases were accidental transections during surgery and were caused by surgical instruments. The present case was different in that the transection happened in the post-operative period and was caused by the patients biting on the tube. The problem multiplied because of migration of the proximal end and obstruction of the tube due to bite leading to the emergency situation.

Conclusion: Flexometallic tube continuation in to the postoperative recovery period is not devoid of risk and emergence biting may lead to airway emergency. As replacement of such tube with PVC tube at times may not be always feasible, it is therefore suggested that continuation with such a tube should only be under strict vigilance in post-operative period.

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